

A Semiotic Analysis of Simulation Levels in the Film *Goodbye Lenin!*

Kamer İncedursun*

ABSTRACT

This article examines the boundaries between reality and simulation by applying Jean Baudrillard's simulation theory to Wolfgang Becker's film *Goodbye Lenin!* (2003) from a cinematic semiotics perspective. The film narrates the story of the main character Alex's attempt to recreate and idealize the old socialist order for his mother Christiane, who has just emerged from a coma, following the collapse of the socialist regime in the German Democratic Republic (East Germany). This process of recreation transforms into a construction of hyperreality that parallels the four stages of simulation detailed in Baudrillard's theoretical approach. The article provides examples of scenes considered to fit the four-stage simulacrum order and uses a semiotic analysis method to reveal the layers of simulation in these scenes. At the same time, connections are established between these layers and the accompanying ideological indicators, symbols, and psychological transformations of the characters. Evaluated within a historical and political context, these layers reveal, at a microcosmic level, how the perception of reality is manipulated and reconstructed, particularly through the media. Ultimately, the film *Goodbye Lenin!* presents a complex structure where reality and simulation are intertwined and makes significant contributions to understanding the concept of hyperreality in cinema.

Keywords: simulation, semiotics, baudrillard, hyperreality, *goodbye lenin*

* Assistant Professor, İstanbul Yeni Yüzyıl University Faculty of Communication Radio, Television, and Cinema Department
kamerincedursun@gmail.com, ORCID: 0000-0001-7083-2206

Goodbye Lenin! Filmindeki Simülasyon Düzeylerinin Göstergibilimsel Analizi

ÖZ

Bu makale, Wolfgang Becker'in yönettiği *Elveda Lenin!* (*Goodbye Lenin!*, 2003) filmi üzerinden sinema semiyolojisi perspektifinden Jean Baudrillard'ın simülasyon teorisini ele alarak gerçeklik ve simülasyon arasındaki sınırları incelemektedir. Film, ana karakter Alex'in, Alman Demokratik Cumhuriyeti'nde (Doğu Almanya) sosyalist rejimin çöküşünün ardından komadan yeni çıkan annesi Christiane için eski sosyalist düzeni idealize ederek yeniden yaratmaya çalışmasını anlatır. Bu yeniden yaratma süreci, Baudrillard'ın teorik yaklaşımında ayrıntılı olarak anlatılan simülasyonun dört aşamasına paralel bir hipergerçeklik inşasına dönüşür. Makale, dört aşamalı simülakrlar düzeniyle örtüşen sahnelerden örnekler sunar ve bu sahnelerdeki simülasyon katmanlarını ortaya çıkarmak için semiyotik bir analiz yöntemi kullanır. Aynı zamanda, bu katmanlar ile karakterlere eşlik eden ideolojik işaretler, semboller ve psikolojik dönüşümleri arasında bağlantılar kurulur. Tarihsel ve politik bağlamda değerlendirildiğinde, bu katmanlar, özellikle medya aracılığıyla, gerçeklik algısının mikrokozmik düzeyde nasıl manipüle edildiğini ve yeniden yapılandırıldığını ortaya koymaktadır. Sonuç olarak, *Goodbye Lenin!* filmi, gerçeklik ve simülasyonun iç içe geçtiği karmaşık bir yapı sunmakta ve sinemada hipergerçeklik kavramının anlaşılmasına önemli bir katkı sağlamaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: simülasyon, semiyotik, baudrillard, hipergerçeklik, *goodbye lenin*

Introduction¹

Theoretical approaches become instrumental in the analysis of cinema films, enabling the creation of multiple, layered, and fluid meanings. This possibility is one of the prime examples that best illustrates the symbiotic relationship between the social sciences and art. Although the idea that art transcends theory and cannot be confined within its boundaries is strongly advocated, theory does not claim to simplify art by reducing it to specific categories; rather, it seeks to reveal the invisible connections between the work of art and history in the broadest sense by looking at it from different angles. For this reason, art is always elusive in a metaphorical sense, while theory and meaning strive to capture it.

Cinema, which has established itself as the seventh art, is a system of signs that goes beyond being merely a narrative tool; it is a system in which social memory, ideology, and the perception of reality are reproduced (Stam, 2000). In this sense, cinema is one of the rare narrative forms that can directly engage with both the individual and collective unconscious. Thanks to this special relationship it establishes with the audience, it conveys not only the visible story but also the historical, cultural, and political codes behind that story. In this context, cinema offers a rich field of analysis for theory, while also becoming a medium that challenges the limits of theory and drives it towards new intellectual openings. Particularly with the influence of postmodern theory, ideas such as the increasing fragmentation of the perception of reality and the replacement of reality by simulation have necessitated new forms of reading in the field of cinema. Baudrillard's concept of simulacra argues that modern individuals are increasingly living in an artificial and representational world, and that the impact of this situation on cinematic representation is becoming increasingly apparent (Baudrillard, 1994).

The film *Goodbye Lenin!* (Dir. Wolfgang Becker, 2003) addresses the fall of the Berlin Wall and the reunification of Germany through the lens of an individual family tragedy, while also providing a platform on which the concept of simulation can be scaled in cinematic terms. The film, on the one hand, addresses Germany's political transformation within a historical context, while on the other hand, it focuses on the psychological and emotional effects of this major transformation on ordinary individuals. This multi-layered structure reveals that cinema is not only a representation but also a means of reproduction. The film's metaphorical language, rather than directly reflecting the unbearable truth, draws on the remnants of reality to portray a young man's struggle to maintain a broken heart and a disoriented mind

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in the face of reality. The film's main character, Alex, bends the truth by blending ideal socialism with the leftover objects of real socialism. Thus, like images reshaped in a mirror, the re-formed image of the German Democratic Republic serves to manipulate his mother for a while longer.

Christiane, a staunch supporter of the German Democratic Republic (GDR), the Eastern Bloc country closest to the Western world, is selected as an example in the film. Rather than confronting the unbearable and inevitable reality brought about by the process of dissolution experienced by all Warsaw Pact countries in economic, political, cultural, and historical terms (the process of the Democratic German Republic being overrun by capitalism).

Christiane's approach is also a psychological defense mechanism. This protective reflex stems from the deep anxiety experienced by individuals who find themselves vulnerable and insecure in the face of an unknown world, following the collapse of political systems that represent grand historical narratives—a collapse that has also been harshly criticized by postmodern thinkers. Lyotard's critique of modernity, particularly his notion of the end of grand narratives (Lyotard, 1984), allows us to understand the theoretical and historical basis of Christiane's trauma. From this perspective, the film is not merely a portrait of an era but also serves as a mirror revealing the individual's helplessness in the face of history.

The simulated universe in the film should not be seen merely as Alex's individual choice. It is also a collective response to the ideological collapse of an era (grand narratives) and the artificial reality offered by the new world order. This is because Alex's neighbors, who quickly reap the benefits of capitalism, also join the simulation game of the German Democratic Republic, which Alex has rebuilt in accordance with his own utopia. Thus, together, they open an aestheticized socialist umbrella against the invasion of capitalism, at least for a certain period of time. Jean Baudrillard's concept of hyperreality comes into play here. Hyperreality defines a plane dominated by simulations that appear more real than reality itself (Baudrillard, 1994). The world Alex creates perfectly reflects this plane: an artificial yet ideal socialist East German world constructed through nostalgia in the face of the absence or cruelty of reality. This world bears the traces of a system that no longer exists (devoid of origin or reference), yet simultaneously offers an alternative space to the oppressive reality of the new system.

In this context, *Goodbye Lenin!* can be evaluated as a film that questions the reflections of historical traumas on the individual and the strategies for coping with these traumas. It is also a powerful example of cinema's representational power and how this representation can be interpreted on a theoretical level. This analysis of the film reveals both the functional and critical dimensions of the relationship between

art and theory. When theory is positioned not as something that limits art, but as a tool that seeks to understand it more deeply, it becomes indispensable for deciphering a multi-layered narrative form such as cinema.

The aim of this study is to understand the emotional, social, and cultural transformations that emerged during the *German reunification* process in the film *Goodbye Lenin!* and to comprehend how post-socialist identity is represented through cinema. The significance of the study lies in establishing a theoretical bridge between memory studies and simulation theory by discussing the psychological, sociological, and economic traumas of East German society through cinematic representation. However, the study's limitations stem from the fact that the data is based on qualitative observations and that cinematic representation directly generalizes social reality.

Literature Review

Goodbye Lenin! is a 2003 German film directed by Wolfgang Becker. Daniel Brühl and Katrin Sass play the leading roles. The film blends the political atmosphere of the period with an ironic and dramatic family story, constructing a collective historical narrative through individual traumas. Therefore, it can be considered not only a family story but also a narrative that reveals the rewriting of social memory. Cinematically, its structure, which blends nostalgia, humor, and tragedy, has resonated widely both nationally and internationally.

The fall of the Berlin Wall and German reunification created a major socio-psychological rupture for East German society. During this period, East German society was shaken not only by the change in the political regime but also by all the dynamics of daily life. Research shows that after reunification, life satisfaction among East Germans declined significantly, social trust was shaken, and this effect continued in the long term (Beutel et al., 2022; Wetzel et al., 2022). The psychological effects created a deep sense of insecurity in individuals, sociologically weakened social solidarity, and economically caused great devastation.

Following reunification, depression, insecurity, and a sense of "second-class citizenship" became widespread among East Germans (Beutel et al., 2022). This situation also fueled nostalgia for the past, expressed through the concept of *Ostalgie*. Furthermore, analyses of life satisfaction reveal a marked decline in the early years of reunification and show that this effect is related not only to economic losses but also to crises of identity and belonging (Hahm et al., 2024). During this process, young people in particular experienced uncertainty about their future prospects and a fragmentation of their cultural identity.

The East German economy faced serious devastation after reunification. Industrial production declined dramatically, unemployment rates rose rapidly, and most East German businesses either closed or became branches of Western companies (Wetzel et al., 2022). This situation led not only to the loss of economic independence but also to the deepening of social stratification. The income gap between the West and the East remained unclosed for a long time, creating a persistent sense of inequality among Eastern individuals.

According to Baudrillard, the simulacrum is no longer a reflection of reality but a representation that replaces reality. In this context, hyperreality is a plane where the boundaries between reality and representation have disappeared (Ren, 2025). Simulacra may have referred to a reality in the past, but today they have become independent signs that exist on their own. Thus, society lives in a universe of images that bear traces of reality but are no longer real themselves. Baudrillard's approach is seen in the microcosm created by the character Alex in the film *Goodbye Lenin!*, who reconstructs a reality that no longer exists at a virtual level (a reality created with images and objects independent of their referents).

Gerry Coulter, in conveying Baudrillard's views on cinema, notes that the pursuit of technological realism has undermined the quality of the cinematic image, but at the same time has made hyperreality visible in cinema (Coulter, 2010). Mike Gane's work, meanwhile, highlights that Baudrillard's media theory, when applied to cultural representation, provides a useful tool for explaining cinema's hyperreality experience in postmodern societies (Wolny, 2017). In this context, cinema functions not only as an art form but also as a laboratory for understanding the effects of the simulation universe on individuals.

In this context, *Goodbye Lenin!* creates a nostalgic simulation while also exemplifying a world where images replace reality on the hyperreality plane. The artificial East Germany created in the film has now been detached from its historical referent, yet it still offers individuals a livable alternative reality space.

The Social, economic, and psychological effects of German reunification

The reunification of Germany is considered one of the most important political events in Europe in the last quarter of the 20th century. The fall of the Berlin Wall in 1989 and the reunification of Germany in 1990 marked not only a process of political integration but also the beginning of profound social, economic, and psychological transformations.

The reunification process brought to light the social structural differences between East and West Germany. Individuals living in East Germany, in particular,

encountered difficulties in integrating into West Germany's capitalist system after reunification. This situation led to the emergence of a phenomenon known as *Ostalgie* (nostalgia for East Germany). Individuals living in East Germany missed the security and stability provided by the old system (Beutel et al., 2022). Furthermore, the reunification process particularly affected women. While women in East Germany enjoyed rights such as equal pay and childcare, these rights were largely lost after reunification, putting women at a disadvantage in the labor market (Wetzel et al. 2022).

Reunification fundamentally changed Germany's economic structure. East Germany's old industrial infrastructure was rapidly privatized after reunification, and many businesses closed. This led to high unemployment rates and economic inequalities. For example, in the early 1990s, the unemployment rate in East Germany was twice that of West Germany (Burchardi & Hassan, 2013). Individuals living in West Germany after reunification enjoyed higher income levels and better living standards compared to those in East Germany. This economic inequality led to social tensions and identity issues. Individuals living in East Germany, in particular, felt economically marginalized during the reunification process (Kasinger et al., 2023).

The reunification process also deeply affected individuals' psychological well-being. Significant differences in psychological health were observed between individuals living in East and West Germany. Individuals living in East Germany, in particular, experienced higher levels of stress and depression due to factors such as increased unemployment and loss of social security after reunification (Schmalbach et al., 2021). Furthermore, the reunification process caused individuals to question their sense of identity and belonging. Individuals living in East Germany missed the security and stability provided by the old system, a condition that has been psychologically termed "Ostalgie" (Beutel et al., 2022).

Germany's reunification was not only a process of political integration but also the beginning of profound social, economic, and psychological transformations. The reunification process brought to light the structural differences between East and West Germany, and these differences led to social tensions, economic inequalities, and psychological problems. In this context, understanding the effects of the reunification process is of great importance for better comprehending both the film *Goodbye Lenin!* and Germany's current social and economic structure.

Method

In this study, Wolfgang Becker's film *Goodbye Lenin!* (2003) was examined within the framework of Jean Baudrillard's theory of simulation and semiotic analysis. The

film *Goodbye Lenin!* was selected as the single sample in the study. The reason for this choice is that the film not only reflects a historical event but also presents a multi-layered cinematic text in which individual memory, social trauma, and ideological simulations are intertwined. The film provides a methodologically unique object of study because it makes the psychological and sociological wounds of post-reunification society visible at both the individual and collective levels.

The methodology of the study is based on a theoretical model that combines textual analysis and semiotic analysis techniques from qualitative research approaches. Baudrillard's levels of simulacra and the concept of hyperreality were used as a theoretical basis, particularly in analyzing the forms of representation of reality; the film's representations were analyzed in terms of how they reproduce the construction of fake reality and ideological cover-ups (Baudrillard, 1994).

Within the scope of the research, the film's narrative structure, character representations, spatial arrangements, and visual-textual relationships were evaluated from a semiotic perspective. In this regard, based on Roland Barthes' semiotic approach, specific scenes in the film were analyzed by separating them into signifier and signified levels (Barthes, 1972). In particular, elements such as the re-representation of the German Democratic Republic (East Germany), the visual symbols of socialist ideology, the use of media, and the construction of memory were linked to simulation theory; the contexts of these elements within the film were subjected to analysis. The process of re-staging East Germany in the film to preserve the reality of the mother has been analyzed in light of Baudrillard's concepts of third and fourth level simulacra; the effects of this false reality on individual and collective memory have been evaluated.

Furthermore, attention has been paid to the historical and ideological contexts of cultural signs during the analysis process. Semiotic analysis aims to reveal not only the superficial meanings of symbols in the film, but also how these symbols are loaded with historical and cultural codes and what meanings they convey to the audience (Chandler, 2017). In this context, the film was treated as a text; all visual and verbal elements were examined within the framework of multi-layered sign systems. Methodologically, the film scenes were analyzed directly; the narrative breaks, symbols, and character behaviors in the film were interpreted in the context of simulation theory and semiotics. This methodological approach, linked to postmodern theory and media representation studies, also carries interdisciplinary value in demonstrating how simulation theory can be applied to cinematic texts (Poster, 2001; Kellner, 1989).

Reality and simulation

Baudrillard states that in the 1960s, Western societies entered a different era in

economic, political, cultural, and historical terms, and that existing theoretical frameworks (especially Marxism) were insufficient to understand the objective conditions in which Western societies found themselves. Baudrillard emphasizes that the principle of reality, which previously enabled Western societies to progress toward a collective social future, has disappeared both ethically and objectively since the 1960s due to radical transformations in the production and social dynamics of traditional capitalism. Terms such as simulacrum, simulation, and hyperreality constitute the conceptual vocabulary Baudrillard uses to articulate the historical and psychological context that has replaced the principle of reality (Adanır, 2008, p. 33).

Jean Baudrillard, particularly in his work *Simulacra and Simulation* (1994), calls for a fundamental rethinking of the relationship between reality, representation, and media in modern society. According to Baudrillard, contemporary society has transcended natural representations of reality and entered a new universe called “hyperreality”. In this context, “simulation” is not merely a copy of reality but a process that replaces and supersedes it.

Baudrillard defines the concept of "simulacrum" as signs and images that no longer refer to reality but exist on their own (Baudrillard, 1994). In the classical sense, a representation points to a reality; however, for simulacra, there is no longer a reality being signified. At this point, simulation ceases to be a simple copy of reality and becomes a plane that precedes reality itself. Baudrillard explains this process with the concept of "precession of simulacra," meaning "the precedence of simulacra": Representation no longer follows reality; on the contrary, it becomes the element that shapes reality.

In this context, the concept of “hyperreality” refers to a new order that emerges when simulations replace reality in social life. In hyperreality, the distinction between reality and fiction disappears; television, advertising, the internet, or virtual reality technologies produce experiences that “appear to be real” but are actually just simulations (Baudrillard, 1994).

Baudrillard argues that the principle of reality emerged during the modernization process that began with the Enlightenment and is a collective belief and emotional form oriented toward specific social goals and ideals. Baudrillard states that the Western World succeeded in getting a significant segment of society to accept this principle as a result of the conditions that arose with the age of scientific revolutions, thereby constructing a kind of collective purposeful reason. Baudrillard argues that social systems governed by dialectics in the past were based on certain principles aimed at coexistence and achieving common goals. In such a world, the causality and purposefulness surrounding both the subject and the object form the principle of progress of the social organism. According to Baudrillard, when these

dialectic collapses, there is no longer a basis for maintaining the balance and progress of the social order, and the social system resembles a nebula revolving around its own axis. This perspective represents the realm of hyperreality. In our era, all values, structures, and institutions have lost their intrinsic significance while retaining their superficial qualities (aesthetic appearance). In other words, in this social phase, which possesses all the signs of reality but cannot represent reality itself and has no origin in the context of causality, the entire system is confronted with phenomenological chaos (Baudrillard, 2011; Baudrillard, 2012). According to him, reality, which once had a specific origin and causality, has now disappeared through representations and has been replaced by a new structure called “hyperreality” (Baudrillard, 1994; Bronowski and Mazlish, 2012).

Baudrillard argues that in the 1960s, Western societies transitioned into a distinct era characterized by new economic, political, cultural, and historical paradigms, and that the dominant theoretical frameworks, particularly Marxist theory, were inadequate to comprehensively grasp the new objective and psychological conditions in these societies. He states that the fundamental principle of reality, which facilitated the progress of Western societies toward a collective social future since the early capitalist period, has become invalid both ethically and objectively as a result of the profound transformations in the dynamics of traditional capitalism since the 1960s. In this regard, terms such as simulacrum, simulation, and hyperreality, which he created by going beyond classical terminology and concepts, form Baudrillard's special conceptual vocabulary used to express the historical and psychological plane that transcends the principle of reality.

Baudrillard argues that the principle of reality first emerged during the modernization process initiated by the Enlightenment and historically represents a collective positivist belief system oriented toward specific goals. He argues that this principle of reality gained acceptance among a significant segment of society in the Western world, where conditions shaped by scientific revolutions (technical progress, capital accumulation, and advances in the social sciences, etc.) increasingly facilitated life (Baudrillard, 1994). Baudrillard also argues that social systems, previously governed by dialectical logic (class struggle), were based on certain principles designed to encourage coexistence and the achievement of common goals. Within such a paradigm, the principle of causality and teleology, which encompasses both subjects and objects, has been the driving force of society. According to Baudrillard, the collapse of this dialectical structure has eliminated the foundation necessary to maintain the balance and progress of social order, thus turning the social system into a nebula revolving around its own axis. In Baudrillard's view, in the hyperreal universe, all values, concepts, and institutions retain their formal qualities (appearances) while losing their intrinsic significance (referential system). Thus, the hyperreal universe,

dominated by these simulations that possess all the signs of reality but have no connection to reality whatsoever, faces a profound phenomenological crisis (Baudrillard, 1994; Baudrillard, 2011; Baudrillard, 2012).

Baudrillard's four-stage order of simulacra

According to Baudrillard, the model of social reality in modern societies unfolds in four stages based on the relationship between the image (the imaginary) and reality. The four-stage order of simulacra describes a process that begins with the representational relationship between the image and reality and ends with the image swallowing reality (Baudrillard, 1994).

The image as a faithful representation of reality

In the first stage, the simulacrum represents a faithful reflection of reality. There is a very close connection between the represented object and its image. At this stage, representation is completely dependent on the reality it refers to and has a moral purpose of reflecting it accurately. Icons, religious figures, or classical works of art are examples of simulacra at this level; because at this stage, the simulacrum is a visual or semantic re-presentation of an existing reality (Baudrillard, 1994).

The image as a distorted representation of reality

At the second level, the simulacrum still refers to reality, but this representation is distorted, manipulated, or idealized. Reality is not presented as a faithful copy, as in the first-level simulacrum representation; instead, it is manipulated to create specific effects on the viewer or consumer. At this level, simulacra present reality embellished or transformed. Representations produced in fields such as advertising and propaganda are prime examples of this level (Baudrillard, 1994; Poster, 2001).

The image that conceals the absence of reality

Baudrillard's third level of simulacra in his simulation theory can be defined as the complete severing of the relationship between reality and its representation. At this stage, the sign no longer refers to any reality; it merely carries traces, images, or a dysfunctional likeness of a certain reality that is thought to have existed in the past. After all material and historical ties to reality have been severed, a sign that no longer requires the object or phenomenon it represents begins to act as if it were reality itself. This situation means that the signifier has ceased to be tied to any real reference and has become an independent or rootless structure that exists within

itself and claims to be the truth (Baudrillard, 1994). From this point on, we enter the stage of simulacra, which begin to take the place of reality. Simulacra have no connection to any reality, yet they continue to behave as if they do. However, the objective relationship between the image and reality is completely severed or very weak (Kellner, 1989).

Baudrillard cites Disneyland as a classic representation of third-order simulacra. According to him, Disneyland embodies the symbolic representation of social concepts such as “childhood,” “innocence,” and “American family values”—concepts that no longer exist. However, the historical referents of these values are no longer present. Therefore, these values, which once had a certain reality but are now hollow and fragmented, continue to exist as a nostalgic reality experienced by visitors, circulated within the Disneyland universe. In short, according to Baudrillard, the existence of Disneyland serves to conceal the hyperreality of life in America (Baudrillard, 1994).

An image with no connection to reality (pure simulation universe)

According to Baudrillard, the fourth level of simulacrum is a pure simulation level that creates its own rules. At this stage, signs neither imitate reality nor trace it; on the contrary, signs only refer to other signs, and the process of meaning formation occurs within a closed semiotic network independent of reality (Baudrillard, 1994; Best & Kellner, 1991). Thus, simulation transforms into hyperreality by completely swallowing reality. Hyperreality represents an artificial space perceived as real by individuals, no longer connected to any physical, historical, or experiential reality (Poster, 2001). There is no longer any distinction between reality and simulacrum. Examples of this pure simulation include the acceptance of digitally created characters generated by artificial intelligence as real people, or the experience of identities and experiences in metaverse environments that are independent of the physical world but are lived in an extremely convincing manner (Turkle, 2011). In fourth-level simulacra, all traces of reality are erased; it is no longer about being real, but about appearing real or being convincing, and this situation demonstrates the ontological rupture of the fourth level. Indeed, according to Baudrillard, at this stage, reality cannot be represented at any level, either virtually or objectively, because there is no reality left to represent (Baudrillard, 1994).

Analysis of Alex's simulation universe

The impact of simulation on social memory

Social memory is conceptualized as a fluid structure that enables individuals to interpret their historical experiences within a collective context. Maurice Halbwachs (1992) argues that memory is a socially constructed phenomenon, not an individual one. Within this framework, the film *Goodbye Lenin!* demonstrates how social memory can be manifested and reinterpreted individually through cinematic representation. The alternative reality Alex invents for his mother serves not only as a protective mechanism for him but also as a manifestation of his own nostalgia for East Germany. This also shows Alex's attempt to repair the traumatic cracks embedded in his subjective memory. This nostalgia, which Svetlana Boym (2001) calls *restorative nostalgia*, aims to reverse the flow of time by meticulously reconstructing the past.

Alex's creative simulations throughout the film attempt to synthesize the separation between personal memory and collective history. The collapse of East Germany signifies not only the end of a political regime but also the eradication of a particular lifestyle, traditions, and forms of belonging. In this context, simulation transcends mere deception, functioning as the restoration of a fragmented identity (Huysen, 2003). The objects used in the film—GDR pickles, old newspapers, flags—serve as indicators of the past and, in line with Barthes' (1972) concept of "myth," encompass historical and ideological meanings.

Simulation of space: Berlin as a stage for home, city, and memory

The depiction of spatial dimensions within cinematic narrative creates a concrete context for the simulation process. Berlin is presented as a metropolis where the realms of simulation and reality intertwine, particularly highlighted by its transformation after reunification. The interior of the house, arranged by Alex, becomes a small microcosm of East Germany, now buried in history. This spatial arrangement can be explained by Henri Lefebvre's (1974/1991) theory of "the production of space". According to Lefebvre, space is the result of all social relations and is political. Alex's residence serves as a tableau fixed ideologically in a bygone era, removed from the continuity of time.

Similarly, urban landscapes function as manifestations of simulacra. After the fall of the Berlin Wall, emblems of Western culture, such as Burger King advertisements, live displays, and Coca-Cola billboards, spread throughout the city, standing side by side with the colorlessness and monotony of the old East German neighborhoods. Similarly, the scene depicting Christiane's ambulance ride to the hospital serves as a visual representation of the physical transition from the old regime to the new regime in a metaphorical sense. These transitions between spatial contexts convey to the viewer not only a political transformation but also a symbolic trauma (Nora, 1989). The use of space in the film can also be analyzed through Michel de Certeau's (1984)

concept of “practices of interpreting space.” The visual and auditory changes Alex makes to the space are strategic interventions that reconfigure the meaning of the space.

The simulation swallowing reality

The simulated universe Alex creates to protect his mother from capitalist invasion ultimately becomes a manipulation of the perception of reality. This manipulation transforms into a regime of knowledge-power that controls his mother's world from a single center (Foucault, 1977). Alex engages in a kind of ideological engineering by editing the news, designing the house, and filtering his mother's world. Although the simulated universe Alex offers his mother is more acceptable and psychologically safe, as Baudrillard (1994) warns, simulation, at a certain point, makes the return of truth impossible. In the film, this impossibility comes to an end with the mother's death. Truth has been lost in a way that can no longer be reversed in a historical sense.

Scene number	Scene Title	Analysis
1	Comatose State and the Collapse of the GDR	His mother's descent into a coma and the collapse of the DDR occur simultaneously. This simultaneity symbolizes the collapse of reality and the disconnection of individual memory. This situation exemplifies Baudrillard's third level of simulacra, where representation begins to give way to simulation.
2	Rebuilding East Germany at Home	Alex constructs a fake GDR simulacrum at home to protect his mother. This is the establishment of a completely artificial universe that no longer references any reality, pointing to Baudrillard's fourth-order simulacrum.
3	Creating Fake News Bulletins	Artificial television news manipulates the truth. These news simulacra, which replace reality, serve to conceal the collapse of the systems that transmit them.
4	DDR Architecture and Interior Design	DDR products used in home decoration are no longer merely nostalgic elements; they create a new universe of meaning. Indicator systems function independently of reality.
5	Coca-Cola Poster and Capitalist Images	The Coca-Cola advertisement is a hyperreal symbol of Western capitalism. This image is not just a product; it is an indicator of a lifestyle and a consumption ideology.
6	Childhood Films and the Broadcast of DDR Programs	The re-editing of old childhood films and television broadcasts means that memory is subjected to simulation. This is the ideological (distorted) reproduction of the past.
7	Special Day Celebrations and Patriotic Songs	Fake flags, GDR anthems, and celebrations create a sense of belonging on a symbolic level; however, this sense of belonging no longer has any real counterpart.
8	The Spiritual Effects of German Unity	The images of German unity seen on television are not an expression of reality for Christiane, but rather the coercive effect of simulation. Hyperreality surrounds

		the individual.
9	Christiane's Death and the End of Simulation	Christiane's death symbolizes the end of simulation. Truth has been irretrievably lost.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Wolfgang Becker's 2003 film *Goodbye Lenin!* is a cinematic text that examines an individual narrative by relating it to ideological, psychological, and social dimensions. The film provides a fertile ground for analyzing Baudrillard's concepts of "simulacrum," "simulation," and "hyperreality" from his theory of simulation. The revival of the collapsed German Democratic Republic (GDR) through simulacra makes it possible to create a simulated universe that replaces reality; this universe is no longer directly related to any referential system.

The visual, spatial, and narrative strategies in the film reveal the workings of simulation and the impact of simulacra, while the psychological fractures of the characters show that this simulation serves not only social but also individual needs. In this respect, *Goodbye Lenin!* does not merely tell the story of an era; it also reveals how simulation replaces reality in a universe where truth has been lost.

Goodbye Lenin! explores the individual reflections of the transformations experienced by East German society after reunification through a nostalgic simulation universe. Baudrillard's concept of hyperreality shows that the world represented in the film is not merely a copy; it is an artificial universe that replaces reality, consumes it over time, and exists on its own.

In this context, the film reveals that cinema is not only a reflection of historical events but also an effective tool in the reconstruction of individual and collective memory. Beyond being a narrative form, cinema functions as a medium that visually and emotionally reproduces a society's relationship with its past, memory, and identity.

Cinema films should be examined in greater depth and comparatively from a historical and social perspective in order to better understand the sociological ruptures that occurred after the collapse of the Eastern Bloc countries and the USSR. It is particularly important to thoroughly examine the process of German reunification in order to understand the current political and economic system in Germany, the most critical geographical region of the Cold War. How are the representations of the *Ostalgie* phenomenon in different films diversified after reunification? How do the representations of nostalgia in cinema in post-socialist societies contribute to the reformation of contemporary political identities?

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